

U.S. ARMY TACTICAL EHF COMMUNICATIONS OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Since the mid-1970's, the U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command (CECOM) has conducted research and development efforts in the area of Extremely High Frequency (EHF) communications for tactical military applications. These efforts have been driven primarily by the need for reliable short to moderate range low probability of intercept (LPI) and jam resistant communications in a variety of applications ranging from line-of-sight multichannel transmission for down-the-hill radio remoting to short range, omnidirectional, covert push-to-talk voice communications for combat net radio users. Development has been concentrated in two frequency bands available for military communications: 36.0 to 38.6 GHz and 54.25 to 58.20 GHz. A number of EHF communications systems in both bands have been successfully developed and extensively tested in both the laboratory and tactical military environments. Test and evaluation results prove that reliable EHF battlefield communications are feasible from the standpoints of both hardware and environment (including propagation), and show that operation in the EHF band provides unique advantages not present at lower frequencies. This paper will describe and discuss the applications and demonstrated advantages of the EHF spectrum, and CECOM's efforts to exploit this band for tactical terrestrial military communications.

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INTRODUCTION

Modern military operations on today's electronic battlefield rely more heavily than ever before on efficient utilization of the RF spectrum. As communications and electronic warfare requirements increase, so does the crowding of the RF spectrum, placing a heavier burden on spectrum managers and systems designers. Further challenges confront the systems designer in the form of greater numbers of more and more sophisticated electromagnetic countermeasures (ECM) systems in the form of direction finding and jamming equipment. For these reasons, CECOM is conducting an ongoing research and development program in the area of extremely high frequency (EHF) communications as a means of improving the spectrum availability problem and decreasing the vulnerability of both multichannel and single channel tactical radio communications to ECM techniques.

The vulnerabilities and limitations of multichannel communications

systems are well documented. The radio terminals are susceptible to jamming, and direction-finding location with subsequent destruction by artillery. As "smart weapons" utilization increases, the enemy will concentrate more on site destruction, and less on jamming. In order to survive, the command and control functions of the tactical Army must be removed from the proximity of the "smart weapons" targets, the signal hills. Tactical CP must be dispersed over large areas of the battlefield. Thus, if remoting and dispersal are invoked, the loss of the command structure and associated C2 assets will occur. Narrower bandwidth equipments (HF, TACSAT, etc.) would provide emergency reduced communications to echelons above and below, until the lost multichannel node is re-established.

EHF communications can play a vital role in the dispersal and remoting needs of the command post. This has been a major driving force in CECOM's EHF technology thrust area. The Multichannel Command

Post Radio (MCPR) member of CECOM's tactical EHF radio family specifically addresses these needs. The MCPR provides increased communications flexibility, enhanced command unit survival, reduced logistics problems, and higher mobility capability to meet the needs of dispersed communication requirements.

Moving closer to the forward edge of battle, the reliance on LOS multichannel substantially diminishes (because of the mobility and communications coverage requirements) and combat net radio (CNR) communications (VHF, HF) are relied upon for C3. Since these are generally omnidirectional radio transmissions very close to the enemy ECM threat, they become even more vulnerable through the utilization of direction finding equipment leading to either radio destruction, signal jamming, and/or loss of surprise. Here, CECOM's EHF technology thrusts are directed to providing "radio silence" (extremely low probability of detection and intercept, jam free) local area C3 for platoon and small tactical CP operations.

ADVANTAGES OF EHF COMMUNICATIONS

As stated previously, the role that EHF can play in the survival of C3 functions is in providing mobile, low probability of intercept, jam resistant communication and assemblage dispersal capabilities to command units. To answer why EHF should be utilized instead of

lower portions of the spectrum, the advantages of EHF must be discussed.

Frequency Availability/Bandwidth:

Frequency availability is a serious problem which will only get worse as the communications needs of the battlefield (and the world) continue to grow. There is little room available at microwave frequencies, and essentially no room below for wideband communications to operate in a noninterfering (self jamming) mode. As battlefield data communications requirements continue to increase, the radio frequency availability problem multiplies. EHF has the capability of providing both wideband communications and frequency availability to the tactical user.

Size/Weight:

Operational wavelengths on the order of a millimeter, in combination with advances in solid state technology, have resulted in EHF systems which are small and lightweight. Complete transceivers can be easily held to sizes less than $\frac{1}{2}$ cubic foot using well-developed waveguide components technology. Significantly smaller packages are possible using monolithic technology currently being developed under DoD's Microwave and Millimeter Wave Monolithic Integrated Circuits (MIMIC) program. Monolithic EHF receivers for electronic warfare (EW) applications have already been produced and

demonstrated under the MIMIC program. A promising application for monolithic circuit technology includes the integration of monolithic transceiver front ends directly with printed circuit antennas, resulting in complete integrated transceiver/antenna systems that are smaller and lighter than most existing parabolic dish antennas alone.

Rapid Deployment:

Quick setup of EHF multichannel equipment has been demonstrated with greater than 8 km links established in less than 15 minutes with transceivers mounted on either tripods or masts.

The rapid set-up time is largely attributable to the EHF systems' small size and light weight which greatly enhance their manageability as opposed to heavier and bulkier microwave systems.

RF/Visual Signatures:

Radios having antennas with narrow beamwidths and extremely low back and side lobes significantly reduce the jam and direction finding threats against EHF. The radiation is extremely difficult to find and even more difficult to jam. The visual signatures are minimal since radio/antenna units are less than 1 cubic foot for multichannel radio relay applications and even smaller for netting applications. For short range applications in the 54-58 GHz range, the RF signatures approach zero when one considers stand-off direction finding equipments.

Capabilities of EHF Communications:

Transmission via EHF is in general more dependent on atmospheric conditions than lower frequency microwave and UHF transmissions. Studies and experimentation have demonstrated that the dominant atmospheric propagation factor is attenuation due to rainfall. While the rain attenuation phenomenon is well known, it has often been over-dramatized. EHF systems properly designed to provide adequate gain margins for the geographic areas of intended use will provide satisfactory link availability performance. For example, 36 GHz EHF communications systems developed by CECOM for point-to-point multichannel cable replacement and remoting applications have gain margins sufficient to provide link availabilities of greater than 99.9% for link lengths of 8 km throughout most areas of the globe. With a gain margin of 30 dB, rainfall rates of 16 mm/hr can be tolerated without any signal outage at 8 km. In tropical areas, where heavier rain rates can be expected, link lengths must be shortened to provide equivalent link availabilities. Conversely, in the drier arid, temperate and polar regions, link lengths can be increased and the same availabilities maintained. Thus, although heavy precipitation will cause signal outages in EHF links, the statistical outages can be kept to less than 0.1% (i.e., 9 hours/year) if links are planned for ranges that match the geographical location of intended use (e.g. 8 km for a majority of the world).

An additional factor for consideration regarding attenuation due to rainfall at EHF frequencies concerns the nature of rainfall and the assumptions made when estimating rain attenuation. Many times, the theoretical calculation of rain attenuation assumes the rainfall to be homogeneous over the radio path. It has been shown experimentally that this assumption is typically correct only at very low rain rates. As rain rate increases, however, the rain becomes increasingly cellular in nature, and the corresponding total path attenuation is therefore less than if the rain was evenly distributed over the radio path. The cellular nature of rainfall is most pronounced with heavy thunderstorm downpours. Data obtained at very high rates of rainfall actually indicate that the cellular nature of the rain is such that two or more cells are unlikely to cross a given radio path at the same time and that the excess path attenuation due to the rainfall is actually, to some extent, independent of path length (Ref. 1).

Atmospheric constituents other than rain, e.g. clouds, fog, dust, smoke, smog, etc., have corresponding little or negligible effect on link availabilities (Ref. 2). Snow causes measurable attenuation, but considerably less than that due to rain. Hence, communications systems designed with link margins to satisfy the expected regional rain statistics will be unaffected by snow. Battlefield debris, such as that caused by

munitions detonations in the radio line-of-sight, have been shown to cause temporary signal outages, with recovery occurring in time periods on the order of one to two seconds (Ref. 3).

Atmospheric nuclear battlefield effects have been evaluated for near surface/low altitude detonations. Atmospheric ionization, refractive index fluctuations and dust/debris influences caused by a nuclear detonation will disrupt EHF transmission for a time frame ranging from a few seconds to a worst case of a few minutes. The long term nuclear atmospheric effects that bother the lower portion of the electromagnetic spectrum do not exist for EHF transmission.

Transmission via EHF is inherently line-of-sight (LOS). However, this is true for all microwave frequencies. In order to ensure free space propagation, it is essential that no obstructions occur within at least 0.6 of the first Fresnel zone of the centerline of the transmission path. The radius of the first Fresnel zone is given by

$$R_f = 17.3 \left(\frac{d_1 d_2}{f(d_1 + d_2)} \right)^{1/2} \text{ (meters), (1)}$$

where $d_1 + d_2$ is the total path length (km), d_1 is the location of the obstruction and f is the radio frequency in GHz. Figure 1

shows a plot of the radius of clearance requirements for 3 km LOS radio relay at 1, 5, and 38 GHz.

In addition, multipath caused by ground reflections is less severe for EHF than for microwave transmission (except for very smooth surfaces where the effects are essentially the same) because the shorter wavelengths tend to scatter from the ground instead of reflecting coherently.

Thus the Line-of-Sight restrictions of EHF are commensurate with those of microwave transmissions but with less clearance required and operation closer to the ground more practical.

In the 50-70 GHz range another phenomenon occurs, namely, signal absorption due to oxygen (up to 16 dB per km at 60 GHz). See Figure 2. Here, EHF transmission is severely range limited, a phenomenon that can and has been implemented as an operational advantage. Communications systems can be made to operate over short ranges without stand-off direction finding equipments being able to detect the presence of any communication taking place. Figure 3 shows how the excess signal attenuation due to oxygen absorption limits propagation beyond the intended receiver, thereby resulting in improved LPI/LPD/AJ performance over lower frequency systems where the signal drops off only as $\frac{1}{r^2}$. This "radio

silence" function has been pursued by CECOM in the Mobile Intercept Resistant (MISR) and Wireless Intra-cell Communications System (WICS) programs, and is presently being investigated for application to existing VHF CNR through the use of a frequency converting applique.

EHF Communications Developments:

CECOM's EHF communications development efforts have concentrated on two bands of operation: 36-38.6 GHz and 54-58 GHz. The lower band has been used for wide-band multichannel trunking systems, such as the MCPR, where range is a more important factor than LPI/LPD. Good range performance (approximately 3 km) is possible at this lower band due to the low value of oxygen absorption (approximately 0.2 dB/km) as seen in Figure 2. The 54-58 GHz frequency band is used in applications requiring maximum LPI/LPD/AJ performance. The high value of oxygen absorption (up to 16 dB/km) which makes this performance possible also limits the communications range, so systems operating in this band are limited to short-range applications such as intra-platoon CNR, dispersed command post (CP) communications and wireless local area network (LAN) systems.

Multichannel Command Post Radio (MCPR):

The EHF Multichannel Command Post Radio (MCPR) operates in the 36-38.6 GHz frequency range

providing a multichannel trunk (point-to-point) for tactical down-the-hill remoting, and cable replacement applications, and for utilization in alternate path routing, and remoting of terminals from microwave multichannel radio relay sites. The MCPR interfaces with the TD-660, TD-202, and TD-754 providing 12 or 24 channel trunk communications. A version of the MCPR also has been developed to allow interfacing with TRI-TAC signal formats (NRZ, diphase, dipulse, and bipolar) at data rates from 144 kb/s to 19.2 Mb/s. All tactical MCPR applications are keyed on mobility and survivability requirements as well as performance.

The MCPR hardware is shown in Figure 4. It consists of a base-band radio interface unit (RIU) and a mast or tripod mounted transmit electronics unit (TEU) interconnected by a multi-conductor cable. The TEU contains all of the radio's RF circuitry integrated into a single package with the transceiver antenna, a ten inch diameter Fresnel lens. This antenna provides 35 dBi of gain with a beamwidth of 2.5 degrees. The Fresnel lens antenna provides excellent sidelobe and backlobe performance, thereby enhancing the LPI/LPD features of the radio.

An earlier non-militarized version of the MCPR (the 3800 Series radio) utilizes a screw-on lens assembly, and has an optional 21 inch, 41.5 dBi Fresnel lens antenna in addition to the standard 10 inch

lens. The higher gain antenna can be used for applications requiring maximum range or additional gain margin. Although not militarized, the 3800 Series radio has proven to be rugged and extremely reliable. These radios have been used for telephone trunk remoting applications at Fort Monmouth and for long-term propagation testing at Fort Monmouth and in Europe, and have been operated for continuous periods of up to two years without a failure.

Table 1 summarizes the performance characteristics of the 3800 radio and the MCPR.

Millimeter Wave Integrated Front End (MMWIFE):

In an effort to minimize hardware cost, maximize reliability, and improve producibility and performance repeatability for an MCPR-type front end, CECOM conducted a Manufacturing Methods and Technology (MM&T) program for the development of a Millimeter Wave Integrated Front End (MMWIFE) in 1982-84. This effort performed by M/A-COM Corporation under contract to CECOM resulted in the development of a small, reliable, reproducible, cost effective 36-38.6 GHz tunable EHF front end for MCPR applications.

The MMWIFE consists of separate and independently controllable transmit and receive sections utilizing a combination of waveguide and microstrip technology. The MMWIFE is not a complete transceiver, but

rather an electronically tunable transceiver front end. The MMWIFE accepts a baseband signal from a host radio package and modulates an EHF carrier for transmission. The receiver section of the MMWIFE down-converts the received signal to a 70 MHz IF and outputs this signal to the host radio. All baseband processing, demodulation, etc. is performed by the host radio. A block diagram of the MMWIFE and summary of its performance specifications are shown in Figure 6 and Table 2, respectively.

In addition to the improved manufacturing techniques and system performance mentioned above, an important benefit of the MMWIFE program has been the resulting development and present availability of an off-the-shelf front end that can be used by any radio manufacturer to produce an EHF radio. It is therefore now possible for radio manufacturers with little or no experience with EHF technology to build an EHF radio. This concept was successfully demonstrated through a joint Army/Air Force program in which Loral TerraCom Corporation, under contract to USAF Rome Air Development Center (RADC), performed modifications to their off-the-shelf TCM-608 microwave transceiver to allow operation at EHF using the MMWIFE in place of the radio's microwave front end.

Short-Range, Covert Unit Level Communications:

As discussed earlier, propagation

in the 54-58 GHz frequency band is very suitable for short-range, covert communications. Development efforts utilizing this band for unit level net communications have included the Mobile Intercept Resistant Radio (MISR) and Wireless Intracell Communications System (WICS). The MISR was designed as a push-to-talk voice radio capable of operating at ranges up to 2 km in an omnidirectional mode and to 5 km in a directional point-to-point mode. This radio incorporates an adaptive tuning feature in which the radios automatically tune over the 54-58 GHz frequency range selecting an operating frequency that provides the maximum oxygen attenuation that will support acceptable communications quality. In this manner, the signal overshoot is reduced to an absolute minimum, thereby maximizing the LPI/LPD performance of the system.

Similar to MISR, the WICS utilizes adaptive tuning over the 55-57 GHz frequency band. WICS was designed for application as a command post (CP) dispersal system and operates as a time division multiple access (TDMA) communications net in which an omnidirectional master transceiver communicates with up to five directional slave transceivers, providing party line voice and data (to 16 kbps) communications between the six total terminals. WICS was designed to support communications over a radius of 1 km (master to slave).

CECOM's present EHF development

efforts are concentrating on using the 54-58 GHz frequency band for short-range, covert wireless local area network (LAN) communications and push-to-talk combat net radio applications.

A Wireless LAN effort currently under way is intended to develop and demonstrate a prototype EHF LAN extension capability to support wide bandwidth interconnection of local area networks, initially for dispersed CP applications and, ultimately, for mobile autonomous fighting units (e.g. Armor System Modernization (ASM)). The initial effort is a concept feasibility demonstration to exploit packet network R&D developed by DARPA. The EHF Wireless LAN is also supported by a current Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) program addressing automatic antenna acquisition for dispersed CP applications.

In order to address the vulnerability of VHF CNR to direction finding and jamming while also easing the frequency management problems of the crowded VHF band, CECOM is investigating the use of frequency converting applique technology for VHF radios. By converting from VHF to the 54-58 GHz EHF band, short-range communications with greatly improved LPI/LPD/AJ performance will be possible. Such a capability would enable communications to be conducted in many critical tactical scenarios now requiring radio silence. Some potential applications for an EHF applique include communications for armor, helicopter,

mechanized infantry, and SOF operations. Demonstration and evaluation of the EHF frequency converting applique technology for armor platoon communications are presently planned. This effort will investigate and quantify the quality and reliability of communications and the reduction in RF signature provided by operation with an EHF applique.

CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed the rationale for using the EHF spectrum for tactical military communications, has identified potential applications for EHF communications technology, and has summarized CECOM's past, present, and future EHF tactical communications efforts. Past efforts concentrated primarily on utilization of the 36-38.6 GHz frequency band for multichannel point-to-point trunk communications. Rugged and reliable systems satisfying this requirement have been developed and tested, demonstrating acceptable performance. Current and future requirements are for short-range, covert, unit level communications; hence, development efforts are now directed more toward the 54-58 GHz frequency band. Past experience has demonstrated that EHF communications technology can satisfy tactical operational requirements from the standpoints of both performance and reliability. It is the conclusion of this paper that many of the Army's current and future

requirements for short-range, covert, tactical communications can also be satisfied through the use of EHF technology.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the efforts of Dr. J. Robert Christian and Messrs. John W. Stroyk, and Milan Schwartz, of the U.S. Army Communications-Electronics Command, Fort Monmouth, whose 1983 paper entitled "U.S. Army's Tactical EHF Thrusts" formed a basis for much of this updated paper.

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TABLE 1
 PERFORMANCE SPECIFICATIONS FOR
 MULTICHANNEL COMMAND POST RADIO
 AND 3800 SERIES EHF RADIO

	3800	MCPR
OPERATING FREQUENCY	36/37 GHz	36-38.6 GHz
RF CHANNELS	2	5
TRANSMITTER	VARACTOR-TUNED GUNN DIODE OSCILLATOR	
TRANSMIT POWER	100 mW	100 mW
RECEIVER	SUPERHETERODYNE SINGLE-CONVERSION GUNN DIODE LOCAL OSCILLATOR WITH AFC	
OPERATION	VOICE, DATA, NTSC COLOR VIDEO	
DATA RATES	1200 bps - 20 Mbps	144 kbps - 20 Mbps
ANTENNA	10" DIA. FRESNEL LENS 35 dBi GAIN 2.5° BEAMWIDTH	10" DIA FRESNEL LENS 35 dBi GAIN 2.5° BEAMWIDTH
OPTIONAL ANTENNA	21" DIA FRESNEL LENS 41.5 dBi GAIN 1.1° BEAMWIDTH	N/A
SYSTEM GAIN MARGIN (20 Mbps @ 8 km)	20 dB	20 dB

TABLE 2
MILLIMETER WAVE INTEGRATED FRONT END
(MMIFE) PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS

TRANSMITTER	
FREQUENCY BAND	36.0 - 38.6 GHz
FREQUENCY STABILITY	
FREE RUNNING	+50 MHz
WITH LOCK BOX ACCESSORY	75 PPM
CHANNELS	10
RF OUTPUT POWER	18.5 dBm
RF SPURIOUS	-70 dBc
VARIABLE ELECTRONIC ATTENUATOR	
INSERTION LOSS	0.25 dB
DYNAMIC RANGE	30 dB
RECEIVER	
FREQUENCY BAND	36.0 - 38.6 GHz
CHANNELS	10
MODULE NOISE FIGURE	8.5 dB
INTERMEDIATE FREQUENCY	70 MHz
I.F. BANDWIDTH	+50 MHz

"LOS" CLEARANCE REQUIREMENTS

FIGURE 1
DISTANCE (KM)

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FIGURE 2 - ATMOSPHERIC ATTENUATION AT EHF

SEL Form 1105A-1, 1 Jan 1987

FM 3404-87

Signal Propagation Under Ideal Conditions.
EHF signals fall off faster than VHF signals.

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FIGURE 3 - SIGNAL FALLOFF, EHF VERSUS VHF

Figure 4. Multichannel Command Post Radio (MCPR).

Figure 5. 3800 Series EHF Radio.

FIGURE 6 MMWIFE BLOCK DIAGRAM, FINAL DESIGN